

ONTARIO SMALL CLAIMS COURT DECLARATORY JUDGMENTS FOR © DISPUTES

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Preamble

The Internet, coupled with digitalization,¹ has forever changed the way our society publishes, duplicates and disseminates the majority of works protected by copyright. Historically, substantial amounts of time, money and effort were needed to publish, duplicate and disseminate works. Though these methods still exist today, the Internet provides an alternative method that allows individuals to publish works almost instantly, duplicate them an infinite number of times without any quality loss and disseminate them on a worldwide scale, all for the fixed cost of a monthly Internet service fee.

Though this circumstance might seem to be, *prima facie*, a librarian's utopia, and the reason the 21st century has been defined as the 'information age,' it has also disrupted our society. Generally speaking, it is safe to say that most individuals abide by the law and respect the rule of law. However, these same individuals, when operating within cyberspace, do not respect the rule of law. People use their new-found power to publish, duplicate and disseminate works to infringe copyright, oftentimes blatantly and on a worldwide scale.

The reasons people are not respecting the rule of law within cyberspace is the topic of another paper. Insofar as this paper is concerned, it is clear that until recently, no person could independently infringe copyright to such an extent that it materially disrupted copyright holders' legally protected remuneration; material disruptions could only take place through concerted efforts by many people. This

¹ As opposed to analog technology.

often meant that laypeople did not need to concern themselves with the particulars of copyright law since, even if they technically infringed the law, it was immaterial to the rights holders. It can be argued that historically, though copyright law applied to all persons, it was only applied, and for the most part developed for, professionals.

Now that copyright - an intellectual *property* - must be applied to laypeople, our judicial system will have to develop to facilitate that interaction. Luckily, our judiciary is already well equipped to resolve layperson disputes for both real and personal *property* claims. It does this, in part, by having a clear understanding of the different characteristics of real and personal property. Indeed, the courts are legally constructed to accommodate these differences. For instance, the Ontario Small Claims Court only provides monetary relief except for repossession of personal property. In other words, even though Ontario wants its Small Claims Court to be remedially restricted, and provide only pecuniary remedies, the unique characteristics of personal property requires Ontario to make an exception and provide a non-pecuniary remedy for personal property in Small Claims Court.

Purpose

With the judiciary's differentiation between real and personal property in mind, this paper posits that property created by copyright, specifically within cyberspace, should be differentiated from both real and personal property by the judiciary; the judiciary should resolve layperson copyright disputes in a slightly different way than it resolves real and personal property disputes. Specifically, this paper will analyze the judiciary's treatment of declaratory judgments in layperson copyright disputes governed by Ontario's Small Claims Court ("SCC").

Issues map

The following is a sequential list of the issues this paper seeks to address:

1. How does the *Courts of Justice Act* in Ontario differentiate between the different types of property and how does it relate to copyright?
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2. What are declaratory judgments? -----> p6
3. What are the benefits of declaratory orders for layperson copyright disputes? -----> p7
4. Within the Canadian and Ontario legal system, which courts have the authority to make declaratory judgments for copyright disputes?
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5. What are potential benefits, and possible detriments, of authorizing the SCC in Ontario to make declaratory judgments for copyright disputes?
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1. Different types of property in the *Courts of Justice Act* and copyright-as-property

Courts of Justice Act

Historically, there were two kinds of property: person and real.

The distinction between real and personal property is based on the nature of the right.... Certain property rights to land were classified as real property because the holder of the right could bring a real action to recover the land from someone who was wrongly in possession of it....

The categories of real and personal property continue to be used and are commonly associated with the categories of land and goods. This is because all real property rights are rights to land, while most personal property rights are not.²

The *Courts of Justice Act*³ contemplates SCC powers with regards to those two kinds of property, as is evidenced by: (1) s. 23(1)(b), which allows repossession of personal property; and (2) s. 100, which states that “a court may by order vest in any person an interest in *real or personal property* that the court has authority to order be disposed of, encumbered or conveyed.” [*Emphasis added*].

Copyright-as-property

This paper argues that copyright-as-property is neither real nor personal insofar as the *Courts of Justice Act* is concerned. However, if real and personal are the only two kinds of property that the *Courts of Justice Act* needs to recognize, copyright must be either real or personal. Despite the fact that copyright may seem *prima facie* personal, it does have real characteristics – for instance, it is a lease given by the government that lasts over a lifetime. Additionally, though necessary to appropriately apply copyright to the *Courts of Justice Act*, the real/personal framework is rarely applied to copyright; in 1985, a parliamentary subcommittee stated “that ‘ownership is ownership is ownership’: the copyright owner owns the intellectual works in the same sense as a landowner owns land.”⁴

Though copyright is probably closer to personal property than real property, it is neither personal nor real; its composition is markedly different. Most importantly,

² R. Chambers, *An Introduction to Property Law in Australia* (Sydney: LBC, 2001) at 37-41.

³ *Courts of Justice Act*, R.S.O. 1990, c. C.43, s. 23(1).

⁴ House of Commons, Standing Committee on Communications and Culture, *Report of the Sub-Committee on the Revision of Copyright: A Charter of Rights for Creators: Minutes of Proceedings & Evidence of the Sub Committee on Communications and Culture on the Revision of Copyright* (Ottawa: Supply & Services, 1985) at 9.

copyright does not have the same scarcity issues that both personal and real have since it “is distinct from any property rights in the tangible item to which it relates.”⁵ A copyright owner can have possession of a work at the same time as an infringer if they both have, for instance, mp3s of the work in their possession. Indeed, judges have ruled that taking intellectual property is not actually theft since the owner still possesses the property after it is taken.⁶ Further, moral rights are important rights given to authors in the *Copyright Act*; yet, unlike personal and real property, moral rights cannot be assigned, only waived.⁷

[William] Blackstone, posits that the essence of property lies not just in the right to exclude others, but in a larger set of attributes or incidents, of which the right to exclude is just one. Thus, Blackstone II: ‘The third absolute right, inherent in every Englishman, is that of property: which consists in the free use enjoyment, and disposal of all his acquisitions, without any control or diminution, save only by the laws of the land.’⁸

Because moral rights cannot be assigned, they are not ‘disposable without any control or diminution.’

Fair dealings are rights given to copyright users; copyright owners do not have the ability to restrict users if they are fair dealing. Fair dealing is arguably not a defense; it is a bundle of rights used to balance the owner and user interests. Fair dealing rights are as important as owner and author rights.

Copyright is concerned with balancing the owner and user interests because, in the words of Lord Mansfield, “[W]e must take care to guard against two extremes equally prejudicial; the one, that men of ability, who have employed their time for

⁵ David Vaver, *Copyright Law*, (Toronto: Irwin Law, 2000) at 16.

⁶ *R. v. Stewart*, [1988] 1 S.C.R. 963.

⁷ *Copyright Act*, R.S.C. 1985, c. C-42., s. 14.1(2).

⁸ T.W. Merrill. “Property and the Right to Exclude” 77 *Neb.L.Rev.* 730 (1998) at 730-9 [*Merrill on Property Law*].

the service of the community, may not be deprived of their just merits, and the reward of their ingenuity and labour; the other, that the world may not be deprived of improvements, nor the progress of the arts be retarded.”⁹ Neither personal property nor real property have a similar balance concept, perhaps partially because scarcity disallows this kind of balance.

At times, it may not even be appropriate to consider copyright in the property law context whatsoever. The Supreme Court of Canada is of the opinion that “copyright law is neither tort law nor property law in classification, but is statutory law... Copyright legislation simply creates rights and obligations upon the terms and circumstances set out in the statute.”¹⁰ “Courts must resolve disputes first by reading and construing the *Copyright Act*, without presupposing what result the common or civil law would have reached.”¹¹ Still, it is clear that copyright can and should be considered property-in-law in the correct context.¹² Indeed, since the *Copyright Act* allows all remedies, “common law and equitable rules and principles must be applied to fashion these remedies.”¹³

Analysis

Fair dealing, moral rights and jurisprudence are strong indicators that, though copyright can utilize personal and real property rules and principles, it is not personal or real property. Copyright requires additional rules and principles to be effectual. It is distinctly possible that not all of these rules and principles are as-of-yet created and the judiciary of the future will create them. However, the judiciary

⁹ *Sayre v. Moore* (1785), 1 East. 361n, 102 E.R. 139n.

¹⁰ *Compare Compo Co. v. Blue Crest Music Inc.* (1979), [1980] 1 S.C.R. 357 at 372-73 [*Compo*].

¹¹ *Copyright Law. Supra*, note 4 at 19; see *Bishop v. Stevens*, [1990] 2 S.C.R. 467.

¹² For example, *Planet Earth Productions Inc v. Rowlands* (1990), 73 O.R. (2d) 505 (H.C.J.).

¹³ *Copyright Law. Supra*, note 4 at 20.

will be limited by the rules and principles it creates if its remedial powers are limited.

A fortiori, if we look at ownership as a method of object and phenomenon control, in property or otherwise, then “possession” in a copyright context is about exclusive possession. Indeed, property law academics consider exclusion as property’s *sine qua non* right;¹⁴ academic discussion of copyright often differentiates copyright rights on the basis of whether they are exclusive or not.¹⁵

Because of scarcity, possession of personal or real property is necessarily exclusive; copyright’s lack of scarcity means an owner must have the power to choose if possession is exclusive or not. Therefore, a recovery of possession in a copyright context does not require a return of the property, since it was not taken from the owner. Instead, it requires a return of the exclusive possession of the property to the owner. This can be done by forcing the infringer to abandon his or her possession of the property; there is no need for the owner to repossess. Yet, as an example, s. 23(1)(b) of the *Courts of Justice Act*¹⁶ contemplates repossession for all personal property in SCC but it does not allow for an equivalent remedy-in-substance for intellectual property because it does not contemplate exclusivity.

2. Definition of declaratory judgments

It is *a priori* and self-explanatory that Plaintiffs start actions to seek remedies.

With that said, there are multiple remedies available to Plaintiffs. Judicial

¹⁴ *Merrill on Property Law. Supra*, note 7 at 730-9.

¹⁵ See example Pamela Samuelson et al., “The Copyright Principles Project: Directions for Reform” (2010), Berkley Technology Law Journal, online: Berkley Law <http://www.law.berkeley.edu/files/bclt_CPP.pdf> at 12 [*Copyright Reform*].

¹⁶ *Courts of Justice Act. Supra*, note 2.

remedies are the focus of this paper, but there are also extrajudicial, or self-help remedies, such as recapture of chattels, land re-entry and nuisance abatement.¹⁷

There are four judicial remedies: (1) *damages* are monetary awards and are the most common judicial remedy; (2) *injunctions* force a party to do a task or act in a particular way; (3) *specific restitution* forces a party to return an object or restore a past condition; and (4) *declarations* are formal statements made by a court.¹⁸

Declarations are ‘preventative adjudication’ remedies “meant to avoid future harm, not remedy past harm.”¹⁹

The first characteristic of preventive adjudication is that it provides no relief except for the adjudication itself. In other words, the plaintiff (or petitioner) seeks an opinion that is not accompanied by a remedial order commanding action by the other party. To understand this characteristic, consider what remedial and preventive adjudication have in common. Both end in a judgment—“a final determination of the rights and obligations of the parties.” And this judgment is ordinarily accompanied by an opinion, which is meant to clarify and justify the court’s resolution of the case. But here the similarity ends. In remedial adjudication, the court gives the successful plaintiff something more: a command to the defendant, either to pay damages or adhere to an injunction. By contrast, in preventive adjudication, there is no command: the opinion only expresses how the court has resolved the case. Preventive adjudication is only declaratory....

A second characteristic of preventive adjudication is that the opinion the plaintiff seeks is prospective with respect to harm.

Despite receiving little attention in the legal literature, preventive adjudication is pervasive throughout the law....

Preventive adjudication is intuitively appealing, because it helps people avoid harm and clarifies the law. But there are downsides to deciding cases in advance instead of waiting for remedial adjudication.... One limiting principle is administrative and error

¹⁷ Robert M. Solomon et al., *Cases and Materials on the Law of Tort*, (Toronto: Thomson Carswell, 2007) at 26 [*Solomon*].

¹⁸ *Ibid.* at 25-26.

¹⁹ Samuel Bray, “Preventive Adjudication” (2010), *University of Chicago Law Review*, Vol. 77, No. 3, Online: SSRN <http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1483859> at abstract [*Preventative Adjudication*].

costs; another is the adequacy of discounting (that is, taking into account the uncertainty of future events). People discount for many kinds of uncertainty, and discounting is usually adequate for uncertainty caused by law. But discounting is inadequate when the law causes uncertainty about inescapable threshold questions for human behaviour.... Discounting is also inadequate for uncertainty about *property rights* because of how uncertainty undermines the rationales for having property rules in the first place (such as encouraging efficient investment and information gathering by property owners). In short, where discounting is inadequate, preventive adjudication is especially valuable.²⁰ [*Emphasis added*].

3. Declaratory orders in layperson disputes

In a general sense, declaratory orders enable the judiciary to make determinations before actual harm occurs. Therefore, declaratory orders for copyright can provide a way for society to proactively solve copyright issues before any societal harm occurs. Because of technology's interaction with copyright, coupled with the law's slow reaction time, copyright issues are continually harming society at unacceptable levels; a proactive legal mechanism would help mitigate this harm by: (1) anticipating potentially new harm by dealing with issues before any harm occurs; and (2) finding legal and business solutions to issues to avoid or, in the least, mitigate as much as possible, harm before it occurs.

The following specifically focuses on many of the benefits of declaratory orders in layperson copyright disputes. However, declarations are also beneficial in professional disputes and it should be kept in mind that many of the benefits articulated below are beneficial to professionals as well. The specific benefits of SCC declaratory judgments are in section 5.

²⁰ *Ibid.* at 1282, 1285 and abstract; see also *Black's Law Dictionary*, 858 (West 8th ed 2004); see generally William Baude, "The Judgment Power" (2008), 96 *Georgetown L.J.* at 1807; see example Frederick Schauer, "Opinions as Rules" (1995), 62 *U. Chi. L. Rev.* 1455 at 1465-67.

Declaring if a work holds copyright

Not all works hold copyright. Though it is generally easy to determine if a work is original enough to be copyrighted, if a work is potentially ineligible for copyright, declaratory orders would be useful: (1) to owners if the declaration states if the work is copyrighted or not because it would help them determine how much they wish to invest in the work; (2) to users if the declaration states the work is not copyrighted, since the work will not be protected by copyright and all users can use the work free of copyright restriction; and (3) to users if the declaration states the proposed use is not a use of the work's expression, which is protected by copyright, but the idea, fact or functional design depicted within the work since ideas, facts and functional designs are not protected by copyright.²¹

Safe harbours, notices and take-downs

A safe harbour is a device created to limit the scope of secondary liability caused by technology advancements. The *Sony Betamax*²² case was the first case to use safe harbours in the copyright context. The device has worked and it is expanding via new legislation.²³ Though safe harbours are yet to be officially used in Canada, *Bill C-32*²⁴ indicates that they will be implemented in the near future.

In instances where it is unclear whether a potential user or secondary user can rely on safe harbour, declaratory orders can determine if safe harbour is available before a use, and the potential for liability, actually occurs.

²¹ See generally *CCH Canadian Limited v. Law Society of Upper Canada*, [2004] 1 S.C.R. 339, 2004 SCC 13.

²² *Sony Corp. of Am. v. Universal City Studios, Inc.* (1984), 464 U.S. 417.

²³ *Digital Millennium Copyright Act*, Pub. L. No. 105-204, 112 Stat. 2860 (1998) (codified throughout 17 U.S.C.).

²⁴ *Bill C-32, Copyright Modernization Act*, 3d Sess., 40th Parl., 2010, available online: <www2.parl.gc.ca/HousePublications/Publication.aspx?Docid=4580265&file=4> at ss. 41.25 to 41.26.

Though *Bill C-32* is currently contemplating a notice and notice provision,²⁵ not a notice and take-down provision, it is possible that either a chilling effect for companies with business models similar to YouTube, or a change in legislation, may create a *de facto* take down if a secondary party receives notice from a rights holder. Even if a user receives only notice, not take-down, a declaration that ‘the use is not infringing the rights holder’ would allow the user to be exculpated from any adverse action by the rights holder or an intermediary seeking safe harbour.

Orphaned works

Copyright law exists fifty years after the death of the author, and, if we look at European and American trends, future legislation may extend copyright to seventy or more years after the author’s death. Because of this and other reasons, potential users are sometimes unable to find a copyright’s rights holders in order to license the work. In these circumstances, a declaratory order that the potential user took reasonable steps to find the rights holders could be a way to provide safe harbour for the potential user. This would allow the potential user to start using the work without liability concerns if the rights holders are eventually discovered.

Fair dealing

Though fair dealing is an exhaustive list, it is not always clear if a use is fair dealing. Further, *Bill C-32*’s expansion of fair dealing means that there will be less clarity as to fair dealing’s definition. Since users relying on fair dealing have difficulty proving enough damages if they are incorrectly denied fair dealing to take action against rights holders, fair dealing has, for the most part, developed in

²⁵ *Ibid.* at ss. 41.25 to 41.26.

jurisprudence in circumstances where a rights holder sues a user and the user relies on fair dealing as a defense.

Declaration allows users to become plaintiffs in fair dealing disputes because damages are irrelevant. There are multiple benefits to this: (1) a potential user can have a use declared as fair before the potential user partakes in any use, allowing the potential user to avoid liability exposure; (2) fair dealing will be better defined because precedent will dictate whether future uses based on similar facts are considered fair or not; and (3) by giving users the right to sue to be declared fair, the balance between users and owners is better struck since users should have the right to actively enforce their right to fairly deal.

4. Declaratory judgments in the copyright legal system

Jurisdiction

The *Copyright Act* defines the court as either the Federal Court or the superior court of a province.²⁶ In an Alberta Superior Court decision, Ingram J. stated that the provincial courts have concurrent jurisdiction with the Federal Court to determine all *Copyright Act* civil proceedings.²⁷

In Ontario, the *Courts of Justice Act* confers provincial court powers to the SCC. The SCC has jurisdiction over provincial superior court civil matters in any action for the payment of money under \$25,000²⁸ or the recovery of possession of personal property.²⁹

²⁶ *Copyright Act. Supra*, note 6 at s. 2.

²⁷ *Don Hammond Photography Ltd. v. The Consignment Studio Inc.*, [2008] ABPC 9 at para 2.

²⁸ *SCC Jurisdiction*, O. Reg. 626/00, s. 1(1).

²⁹ *Courts of Justice Act. Supra*, note 2 at s. 23(1).

Remedies

The owner of a copyright is entitled to all remedies available in law for the infringement of a right, explicitly including injunctions, damages and accounts.³⁰ In addition to any damages caused by infringement, the plaintiff can recover the profits the infringer made from infringement.³¹

There are certain limitations on remedies if a defendant is unaware of the infringement.³² Importantly, s. 39(1) disallows any remedy for copyright infringement disputes besides injunctive relief if the defendant did not know or had no reasonable grounds to know copyright subsisted in the work.

S. 96(3) of the *Courts of Justice Act* states that “only the Court of Appeal and the Superior Court of Justice, exclusive of the Small Claims Court, may grant equitable relief, unless otherwise provided.”³³ S. 97 of the *Act* states that “The Court of Appeal and the Superior Court of Justice, exclusive of the Small Claims Court, may make binding declarations of right, whether or not any consequential relief is or could be claimed.”

Though there is not any jurisprudence on s. 97, there has been some jurisprudential discussion regarding s. 96(3) and whether the SCC can provide injunctive relief. In *Weiss v. Prentice Hall Canada Inc.*³⁴ (“Weiss”), the SCC determined in obiter in 1995 that the SCC has jurisdiction to grant injunctive relief for copyright infringement. In *Dolmage v. Erskine*,³⁵ the SCC disagreed with

³⁰ *Copyright Act. Supra*, note 6 at s. 34(1) for economic rights and s. 34(2) for moral rights.

³¹ *Ibid.* at s. 35(1).

³² See *Ibid.* at s.38.1(2) and s. 39(1).

³³ *Courts of Justice Act. Supra*, note 2.

³⁴ [1995] O.J. No. 4188, 66 C.P.R. (3d) 417, [1995] CanLII 7334 (ON S.C.).

³⁵ [2003] O.J. No. 161, [2003] O.T.C. 38.

Weiss in its 2003 judgment based on a distinction between the *Courts of Justice Act* in 1995, when *Weiss* was decided, and the *Courts of Justice Act* in 2003; the old *Act* did not expressly exclude the SCC in its “Jurisdiction for Equitable Relief” section whereas the new *Act* did exclude the SCC.³⁶

The distinction made in *Dolmage v. Erskine* may not have been appropriate. The *obiter dicta* argument in *Weiss* relied on the SCC’s *curia designate* power to enforce civil remedies. In other words, a *Copyright Act* injunction is based on a statutory jurisdiction, instead of the inherent jurisdiction basis for equitable injunctive relief, since it is expressly stated in the *Copyright Act*. Arguably, this is the exact kind of “unless otherwise provided” contemplated by s. 96(3) of the *Courts of Justice Act*.³⁷ *A fortiori*, as previously mentioned, the Supreme Court of Canada defined copyright not as tort law or property law but as statutory law.³⁸

*936464 Ontario Ltd. (c.o.b. Plumbhouse Plumbing & Heating) v. Mungo Bear Ltd.*³⁹ (“*Mungo Bear Ltd.*”) is a London, ON 2003 Ontario Superior Court of Justice Divisional Court case that dealt with an appeal to an injunction granted in SCC. The appeal was dismissed. In the decision, Heeney J. stated that the only injunctive relief the SCC is disallowed to issue is injunctive relief originating in equity. Heeney J. argued that a *quantum meruit* is derived from the common law, not equity, so the SCC can issue *quantum meruit* injunctions because s. 96(3) has

³⁶ Though the *Weiss* case was decided in 1995, the 1990 *Courts of Justice Act* s. 96(3) was applied in the decision instead of the 1994 *Courts of Justice Act*’s s. 96(3).

³⁷ *Enrietti-Zoppo v. Colla*, [2007] O.J. No. 5183, 63 C.P.R. (4th) 377 is another SCC case that states the SCC does not have injunctive powers for copyright. The case relied on s. 96(3). However, the court dealt with the issue briefly in one paragraph. It did not contemplate the meaning of “unless otherwise provided” nor any other possible reason for an exception to the rule that SCC cannot provide injunctive relief.

³⁸ *Compo. Supra*, note 9 at 372-73.

³⁹ [2003] O.J. No. 3795, 74 O.R. (3d) 45.

no application.⁴⁰ As aforementioned, the injunctive remedy found in the *Copyright Act* comes from statute, not equity.

Heeney J. contemplated the possibility that *quantum meruit* is equitable and presented the following arguments: First, s. 23(1) states that the SCC has jurisdiction in “any action.” Heeney argued that this statement is so broad that it must include equity and common law actions.⁴¹ Second, s. 23(1)(b) gives the SCC power to make orders for the recovery of possession of property, a decidedly equitable relief.⁴² Third, and most importantly, Heeney J. distinguished the *Courts of Justice Act* s. 96(3) from s. 97. S. 97 is the section that prohibits the SCC from making declaratory judgments. Unlike s. 96(3), s. 97 does not have an “unless otherwise provided” caveat. Consequently, the court created a blanket prohibition on the SCC making declaratory judgments.⁴³ Heeney J.’s argument was that if the legislature did not want the SCC to issue any equitable remedy besides damages, the legislature would not have included the s. 96(3) caveat.

Analysis

There are no jurisdictional issues with the SCC hearing copyright disputes. S. 23(1) of the *Courts of Justice Act* gives the SCC jurisdiction for any action. Further, *Weiss* and *Dolmage v. Erskine* are examples of SCC cases that dealt with copyright disputes.

Declaratory judgments are not explicitly enumerated in the *Copyright Act* but because the act states that all remedies are available, even if they are not

⁴⁰ *Courts of Justice Act. Supra*, note 2 at paras 12-15.

⁴¹ *Ibid.* at paras 25-26.

⁴² *Ibid.* at para 27.

⁴³ *Ibid.* at paras 30-31.

specifically mentioned, it is highly probable that declaratory judgments are available.

Though s. 39(1) of the *Copyright Act* disallows declaratory remedies, this may be a minor issue in practice. A simple phone call to an infringing party by a potential Plaintiff before an action is commenced would deny a defendant the ability to rely on s. 39(1) for any harm subsequent to the phone call. Further, a notice and take-down or notice and notice would also deny the defendant the ability to rely on s. 39(1) for harm caused after notice. Finally, in circumstances where a Plaintiff is a user that seeks a declaratory judgment regarding the Plaintiff's right to fair dealing, the proceeding is not for the infringement of copyright nor is the defendant unaware of copyright since the matter regards the defendant's copyright and so s. 39(1) does not apply.

It is clear from *Weiss, Dolmage v. Erskine* and Heeney J.'s analysis in *Mungo Bear Ltd.*, that regardless if copyright injunctive relief is available in SCC, declarations are not. Even if the *Copyright Act* specifically listed declaratory relief, the s. 97 of *Courts of Justice Act's* prohibition against SCC declarations does not have the "unless otherwise provided" exception found in s. 96(3).

5. Reasons for and against declaratory judgments for copyright in SCC

Judicial activism

The most convincing reason to allow declaratory judgments for copyright in SCC is the reality that Copyright legislation has been unable to keep up with technological advancements. Recent history has shown us that future technology disrupts copyright in ways the legislature cannot imagine. It is doubtful that even if *Bill C-32* succeeds, this reality will change.

Though judicial activism should be kept to a minimum because it is undemocratic, it provides a way to fill in the gaps in legislation, either because the drafters were unclear or because technology has disrupted the functionality of the legislation. By allowing a sensible amount of judicial activism within the SCC, with the potential to appeal in superior courts, copyright law will be better equipped to adapt to changing technologies.

Finally, the evolutionary characteristic of the common law – where only the fittest judgments survive superior court appeals – means that common law solutions to new problems will most likely be functional and balanced. Where the common law solutions are not functional and balanced, the legislature can amend through the *Copyright Act*.

Discretion

If a SCC judgment is inappropriate, especially the activist judgments proposed throughout this paper, parties might decide to appeal all the way up to the Supreme Court of Canada. Since superior courts have the right to deny an appeal, they have discretionary powers to determine the cases they will hear. Further, superior courts cost more money so parties will have stronger incentives to settle out of court, perhaps creating viable business solutions for future circumstances of similar nature. Therefore, by allowing more SCC decisions, the superior courts will not have ‘more copyright cases to deal with’ but, instead, ‘more copyright cases to choose from.’ This will make it easier for superior courts to choose cases that deal with important copyright matters with favourable fact patterns for judgments designed to modify common law.

SCC's structure

Because declaratory judgments have no monetary element, they are very costly. Plaintiffs will not recuperate legal fees, nor will they recuperate opportunity cost. Though costs are still present in SCC, they are not nearly as high; SCC was created, and is designed to, lower costs. Laypeople can self-represent in SCC which also lessens costs.

SCC is designed to pressure parties to settle out of court. SCC requires a Mandatory Settlement Conference, usually one month after the statement of defense is filed, where opposing parties meet in a less formal setting with a Deputy Judge and try to come to a settlement.⁴⁴ Imposing settlement incentives on parties before and during trial forces parties to find solutions, both business and lay, that mitigates harm to both sides as much as possible.

Overall, the SCC is designed to be much more expedient than superior court. The SCC achieves this goal via various methods, including: (1) fewer rules than superior proceedings; (2) more flexibility with rules than superior proceedings; (3) less time in trial than superior proceedings; and (4) fewer motions than superior proceedings.

Since SCC is already available to all Ontario citizens, SCC is able to provide copyright declaratory judgments to Ontario laypeople as soon as it is authorized to do so. Since the Internet has made it so that all Ontarians have to now interact with copyright, it seems appropriate to provide all Ontarians with appropriate adjudication for copyright disputes. In fact, from this perspective, it is arguable

⁴⁴ *Rules of the Small Claims Court*, O. Reg. 505/09 at s. 13.

that it is a *Charter*⁴⁵ obligation of the government to provide appropriate adjudication if it is subjecting its citizens to legal penalties.

Further, because the SCC is an official part of the judiciary, its rulings create persuasive precedent. This means that: (1) courts can save time, effort and costs when making judgments by relying on factually similar precedential cases; and (2) neither SCC nor superior courts are bound by inappropriately decided SCC precedent since those courts have either parallel jurisdiction or superior jurisdiction.

Finally, because the SCC is accessible to all Canadians, not just specialists, it is possible that a greater number of copyright claims in SCC will improve society's understanding of copyright. Laypeople will interact with copyright in SCC and they will, in turn, teach their friends and family about appropriate behaviour: (1) if they are found to infringe since they will want their community to learn from their mistakes and avoid penalties; and (2) if they receive judgments in their favour, or at least judgments they consider fair and respectable, because they are more likely to respect copyright law in general. Laypeople satisfied with their judgments may even enforce the behavioural norms required to respect copyright within their community.

This grassroots socialization will take time, it will not happen overnight. If supplemented with public legal education and other teaching methods, socialization will help laypeople engage with the copyright system. Over time,

⁴⁵ *Canadian Charter of Rights and Freedoms*, Part I of the *Constitution Act, 1982*, being Schedule B to the *Canada Act 1982* (U.K.), 1982, c. 11 at ss. 7-8.

ordinary Canadians will begin to respect and uphold the rule of law in cyberspace as much as they respect and uphold the rule of law in society.

Moral rights

Moral rights are non-pecuniary so they are rarely litigated. If moral rights can be determined in the more cost effective and self-help SCC, then authors may be more likely to avail themselves of their moral rights. Further, since damages are often difficult to determine for moral rights, declarations will be useful remedies to authors. Though declarations do not change an infringer's behaviour, an author with a declaratory order that clearly states a party is infringing a moral right, will be more likely to settle with any infringer since the author's chances at winning in a superior court are greatly improved if the author has a declaratory order from the SCC clearly outlining why the infringer is *prima facie* infringing.

Fair dealing

Section 3 addresses the specific benefits of declaratory orders with regards to fair dealing. With those benefits in mind, the assessment required to determine if a use is fair dealing often requires a complex and fact-specific analysis. The analysis often requires a discretionary balance of party and policy interests. Judges, including SCC judges, are well versed in this type of analysis.

A potential issue is that SCC judges are Deputy Judges, and are often unaware of the unique characteristics and subtlety required to strike an appropriate balance in fair dealing determinations. This means that SCC may not be sufficiently familiar with copyright to provide appropriate fair dealing judgments.

Even if the above is true, the costs and self-help aspects of SCC mean that users and potential users will be more likely to take the Plaintiff's position in fair dealing

disputes. If users and owners switch positions from Plaintiff to Defendant in fair dealing litigation, the jurisprudence will be more likely to reflect a balance between users and owners. For instance, there are many arguments that proof onuses in copyright law are too heavily laid on the user and a more appropriate balance should be sought; this might be because courts only hear cases where owners are harmed by uses, not where users are harmed by an inability to fairly use.

Safe harbours, notices and take-downs

Though Canada may have statutory safe harbours in the near future, the SCC, with a modicum of “judicial activism,” can create common law safe harbours, based on statutory safe harbour principles. This would allow the judiciary to address secondary liability issues arising from new technologies. For instance, a SCC could provide safe harbour from secondary liability for “online service providers that deploy reasonable, effective, and commercially available measures to minimize infringement.”⁴⁶

Further, SCC would allow a user to be cheaply, and relatively quickly, exculpated from a rights holder’s specious infringement accusation.

Finally, since the SCC has the ability, in its discretion, to impose legal costs on a party, overly aggressive rights holders will have a disincentive to over-claim by issuing frivolous and inappropriate infringement notices. Therefore, by allowing SCC to make declarations regarding notice and notice provisions, the chilling effect associated with notice and notice might be mitigated.

⁴⁶ *Copyright Reform. Supra*, note 14 at 40.

Orphaned works & technological protection measures

Because the SCC has broad monetary remedial powers at its disposal, the SCC could not only create a safe harbour for a potential user of orphaned works by declaring that the potential user took reasonable steps to find the rights holders, but it could also impose a trust that the potential user must pay into in case the rights holders are located after judgment. To determine if a trust is appropriate, the SCC could look at the specific facts of the case, including whether or not the proposed use is commercial.

With the correct legislation or superior court decision, the law may decide to balance technological protection measures (“TPMs”) interests with technology development interests, requiring TPMs to meet certain standards. If this happens, the SCC could be used “to assess whether a particular technical measure is indeed reasonable, effective, and commercially available.”⁴⁷ In the least, if *Bill C-32* is implemented, the SCC could declare whether a specific TPM circumvention is allowed by the *Copyright Act*.

Law clinics

Student-run, lawyer-supervised *pro bono* law clinics in Ontario law schools are starting to provide legal services for copyright matters. The University of Western Ontario’s Community Legal Services (“CLS”) Intellectual Property, Information & Technology (“IPIT”) Certificate Programme is an example. CLS students can litigate copyright matters in SCC, but they cannot litigate in superior courts. With CLS, laypeople can have legal representation without any legal costs in SCC for copyright matters; they do not need to be self-represented. Therefore, laypeople

⁴⁷ *Ibid.* at 42.

can submit well-articulated arguments, from either the Plaintiff or Defendant side, which will help ensure SCC judgments are well-informed.

In fact, because clinics are associated with law schools, there is a potential for professors specializing in IPIT to work with clinics and help students with their SCC submissions. If this happens, SCC court declarations would be indirectly based on arguments from some of the most eminent copyright minds in Canada.

Finally, CLS's copyright clientele is predominately comprised of *gratis* professional institutions such as "libraries, archives and museums...: cultural institutions created to serve the public good by making books, journals, ephemera, artifacts, and other materials available in order to increase knowledge, taste and culture and to enhance the ability of citizens to interact with the world around them."⁴⁸ These clients often request clarification on whether certain uses are fair dealing in addition to many other questions regarding the clients' operations and proposed operations that copyright law may affect. CLS is frequently unable to provide definitive answers. By allowing clinics to access SCC to acquire declaratory orders for important questions posed by Ontario's cultural institutions, clinics will help, from the ground up, develop copyright law to meet society's ever-changing copyright needs.

6. How to authorize SCC to issue declaratory judgments for copyright

Because the SCC is a subsidiary of the provincial courts, with no inherent power, and because s. 97 of the *Courts of Justice Act* does not have the "unless otherwise provided" caveat found in s. 96(3), no amendment to the *Copyright Act*, a federal statute, will be able to provide declaratory remedies in SCC. Within provincial law,

⁴⁸ *Ibid.* at 56.

there are two ways to provide declaratory orders in SCC for copyright: (1) the *Courts of Justice Act* can be amended to specifically address copyright law and state that declarations are available in SCC specifically for copyright disputes; or (2) a similar caveat can be included in s. 97 of the *Courts of Justice Act* as is found in s. 96(3).

As the conflicting injunctive jurisprudence shows, the s. 96(3) caveat does not necessarily mean that declarations will be available in SCC if s. 97 is amended. It is even more unlikely that an s. 97 amendment will allow declaratory relief since the *Copyright Act* specifically references injunctive relief but does not reference declaratory relief. Because of the foregoing, it is best if the *Courts of Justice Act* is amended by the Ontario legislature to specifically allow copyright, or in the least intellectual property in general, SCC declaratory relief.

7. Alternatives to SCC Declaratory judgments

It is possible for the *Courts of Justice Act* or the *Copyright Act* to be amended to allow the SCC to issue declaratory orders for only certain copyright matters. For instance, if the federal government decides that SCC Deputy Judges do not have the expertise to determine if a use is fair dealing or not, the *Copyright Act* could be amended to explicitly deny declaratory remedies by SCC for fair dealing disputes.

The Copyright Principles Project (“CPP”) recently published a “Directions for Reform” report to the US Congress and the Library of Congress’s Copyright Office. The report lists multiple recommendations, though designed for the US context, that are useful to Canada.

One of CPP's recommendations is that "congress should establish a low-cost adjudication procedure to allow copyright disputes to be resolved without the need for highly expensive federal court litigation."⁴⁹ In the Canadian context, this would mean that the federal government would create an adjudication procedure, separate from the Federal Court, which would act as a specialized SCC. Though this federal SCC would most likely be comprised of copyright specialists, better equipped to handle copyright issues than Ontario SCC's Deputy Judges, the federal SCC would be more geographically limited than Ontario's SCC. Implementing a federal SCC that is available in every courthouse in Ontario, and probably every Canadian province, is probably inhibitory costly and not feasible.

Another CPP recommendation is:

For the Copyright Office to consider providing the public with more guidance about what constitutes "fair use" and what does not. One alternative discussed by the CPP group was having the Office provide fair use "opinion letters." Individuals or firms considering whether a contemplated use of a copyrighted work would qualify as a fair use could submit a request to the Copyright Office for an opinion. The request would provide the relevant facts describing the contemplated use. The Copyright office would meet with the applicant and elicit further information. When the copyright Office felt informed enough to do so, it would undertake a fair use analysis and issue an opinion letter.⁵⁰

In Canadian, the Copyright Office would be the Copyright Board of Canada and fair use would be fair dealing. The opinion letter would be non-binding and it would also be subject to judicial review. However, the Copyright Board of Canada may dislike providing letters that might inadvertently create precedent because the letters would be persuasive - possibly not in the judiciary but within professional circles and perhaps society in general.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.* at 21; see also *ibid.* at 32-33.

⁵⁰ *Ibid.* at 31; see generally *ibid.* at 30-32.

Conclusion

Though beyond the scope of this paper, an expansion of the SCC's jurisdiction over copyright law may provide many benefits beyond those associated with declaratory relief. First, the paper briefly addressed some benefits associated with injunctive relief in the section 1 analysis. Second, damages would be more appropriate for disputes with laypeople. "The unpredictability of statutory damages sometimes has an undesirable chilling effect on some conduct that, if challenged, would be lawful."⁵¹ However, because the SCC caps damages at \$25,000, if a Plaintiff wishes to take advantage SCC's expedited procedure and low costs, the Plaintiff will have to cap his or her damages at \$25,000. Plaintiffs using tactics similar to the RIAA's tactics may decide this option is the more cost effective since it helps with litigation economies and \$25,000 still provides enough disincentive to most layperson infringers to stop them from pirating.

The structure of SCC, mentioned in section 5, can help layperson users and creators. Because the SCC has lower litigation costs, and therefore lower risk, and because SCC Deputy Judges have the discretion to award costs to the winning party, SCC provides a balanced solution to the user-and-owner "chilling effects" contemplated in the following:

"Imprecision in the scope of exclusive rights often makes copyright owners reluctant to sue those whom they reasonably believe to be infringers, owing in part to the cost and uncertainty of litigation. At the same time, the current legal structure makes it possible for an aggressive copyright owner to overclaim rights and to force good faith users or follow-on creators to defend a use as falling within the complex web of existing limitations and exceptions. Overclaiming can impose high litigation costs, including risks of statutory damage awards, and thereby chill some uses that if challenged would ultimately be found non-infringing."⁵²

⁵¹ *Ibid.* at 45.

⁵² *Ibid.* at 34.